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Flow over rough topography

Numerical studies at Ormen Lange

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1 Executive summary

The exploration of the Ormen Lange gas field represent new challenges to the engineers. The field is located off the continental shelf at depths ranging down to 700 meters. In addition, the area was scene for the dramatic Storegga landslide, hence the topography is extremely rough. In addition to the dynamics produced by the sloping continental slope, such rough topography generates additional dynamics that are of importance to design, installation, and maintaining of sub-sea constructions.

The present study aims for comparing model integrations with and without the hydrostatic approximation. This approximation is often used in large scale Ocean General Circulation models (OGCMs), and is valid as long as the horizontal resolution is beyond 10 km (Marshall et al. 1997a). The approximation reduces the vertical velocity to a diagnostic variable. On smaller scales it generally not justified to neglect the dynamical pressure as the vertical velocity must be modeled prognostically.

The simulations presented here were performed on a 400 by 400 meter spatial domain. The MITgcm, a public domain, well supported general circulation model, that allows for non-hydrostatic simulations, was used to perform the simulations. A 1 meter resolution map, obtained by the Norsk Hydro bathymetric survey of the gas field, were used as origin for the topography at the bottom boundary.

In order to save CPU time, the first set of simulations took place with a resolution of 4 meter. To have a closer look on the hill in the center of the domain, at which the data acquisition program was performed, a second set of simulations was performed with a local resolution of 1 meter. In order to simplify flux control, the boundaries for both sets were moved away from the area of interest by stretching the grid, hence less resolution at the boundaries. The vertical grid spacing was 1 meter at the bottom and upward until passing the highest obstacle. Thereafter the grid was stretched to the surface.

It is shown that the difference between the two scenarios are distinct. When the hydrostatic approximation is assumed, the disturbances generated by the topography is allowed to move more freely through the water column. In case of non-hydrostatic modeling energy is transfered between vertical and horizontal directions by the dynamic pressure. It is also seen that the blocking effect increases when the hydrostatic approximation is in place. Without the approximation the current has a higher tendency to move past the object, and a corner effect is seen with increased speed at the lateral sides of the obstacle.

Together with Berntsen and Furnes (2002), this was a first attempt to identify important features of high resolution topographic effects at the Ormen Lange site. Further work should concentrate on three aspects; First, a sharp pycnocline in the area will affect the behavior of internal waves. This may alter the flow field considerably and needs special attention. The interface between Atlantic and the much colder Norwegian Sea water masses, that are likely to enter the area, is not represented in these simulations since a climatological profile is used. If in addition there are waves present on this interface, the dynamics becomes even more complex.

Secondly, studies of time dependent flow field at the boundaries, with possible turning of the flow vector. This may include incoming internal waves and is not straight forward to implement due to possible inconsistency between the boundaries and generation of artificial (numerical) waves.

Finally, a study on how far the boundaries need to be moved away from the interior in order not to influence on the area of interest will be valuable. By selecting a smallest possible stretching of the grid without contaminating the results, simulations at a number of locations along a pipeline can be executed at lowest possible CPU cost.

This report continues with a short overview of the MITgcm, Section 2, describe the numerical setup in Section 3, results from the different grids used will be shown in Sections 4 and 5, and

discussion and conclusions are given in Section 6. Finally, prospect for further studies is given in Section 7, and the report concludes with an appendix with two sections on hydrostatic vs. non-hydrostatic modeling, App. A, and a method for statistical description of sub-grid scale topography in App. B .

2 The MITgcm

The MIT general circulation model (MITgcm), (Marshall et al. 1997a,b) has recently been established as the “in-house” non-hydrostatic (NH) numerical solver at NERSC. It is to our knowledge one of the few NH models that is public domain and continuously evaluated through its daily use at research institutes worldwide (<http://mitgcm.org>). General features of the MITgcm are:

- can be used to study both atmospheric and oceanic circulation
- has a non-hydrostatic capability
- supports horizontal orthogonal curvilinear coordinates
- has a finite volume treatment of topography
- supports a wide range of physical parameterizations
- has tangent linear and adjoint code maintained alongside the forward model
- can run on PC, workstation or parallel computers using flexible domain decomposition.

The important features for this study is the non-hydrostatic capability and the finite volume treatment of topography. The grid cell adjacent to the boundary are “shaved” to avoid the stair case representation, this avoids generation of artificial waves. Another important issue is that the model allows for variable grid spacing in both horizontal and vertical directions.

3 Numerical experiment setup

An area of 400×400 meters, with a resolution of 1 meter, around the location of the in-situ data acquisition program form the basis for all the numerical experiments performed, (Fig 1).

Two different grids have been used; The first covered the whole initial area with an resolution of 4 meter, Fig. 2(a), while the other had a resolution of 1 meter in an area around the center obstacle, Fig. 2(b).

To ensure conservation of water masses and momentum, both grids were stretched in all directions and interpolated towards the average depth at the boundaries. By this exercise all boundaries had the same area, hence flux control was simplified. Vertical resolution was one meter from the bottom until above the highest obstacle, whereafter the grid was stretched to the surface in order to save number of grid cells.

A steady inflow of 0.2 m/s at the long stream boundaries was enforced and initial and boundary conditions for density was taken from climatological profiles, see Fig. 1(b). All simulations ended after one hour integration.

Figure 1: The high resolution bottom matrix and environmental profiles used in the simulations.

Figure 2: The grid is stretched in both horizontal directions and the depth is interpolated into the resulting grid in way that approaches mean depth at the boundaries.

4 Results with 4 meter resolution

After one hour integration the flow field was in a quasi-steady state and all results were taken as snapshots at 60 minutes. Data is only shown for the area of interest, as shown in Fig. 3, hence the stretched part of the model region is neglected in the following.

Figure 3: *The area of interest and along stream cross sections shown in Fig. 4*

Fig. 4 compares the hydrostatic and non-hydrostatic simulations at different along stream cross-sections, shown as white lines in Fig. 3. The color bar shows speed normalized with the boundary enforced velocity, 0.2 m/s , and the gray contour line represent a normalized speed of unity. The most evident difference between the hydrostatic and non-hydrostatic simulations is the higher variations of speed in the former. Another difference is the reduced speed at the upper part of the figures for the hydrostatic simulation.

The cross-section at 293m passes directly over the hill at which the measuring program by Norsk Hydro was performed. Notice the increase in speed as the flow passes the obstacle. For the hydrostatic case the gain of speed propagate upward through the water column, while in the non-hydrostatic case the area with increased speed stays more focused on top of the hill.

The reason for these differences is due to the way internal waves are able to propagate. The elliptic solver used in non-hydrostatic simulations, necessary to obtain the dynamic pressure, represent a mechanism for transfer of energy between the two horizontal directions and the vertical. The hydrostatic assumption removes this mechanism, hence reduces the resistance felt by vertical component of the current.

Fig. 5 illustrates this further. In the hydrostatic case; the maximum speed is seen just above the logarithmic layer and the speed stays above unity for approximately 200 meters. Above this layer the speed reduces below unity before again go above the background speed. In the non-hydrostatic case we see much the same features, however the vertical stretching of the “wave” has less extent in the vertical and the amplitude of increase and decrease is lower. The vertical propagation of waves are suppressed.

Normalized speed 5 and 10 meters above bottom are shown in Fig. 6. At 5 meters above the seafloor the speed is higher on top the obstacles in the hydrostatic compared with the non-hydrostatic case. Notice the difference in speed in the vicinity of the hill in the center of the domain 10 meters above the bottom. In the hydrostatic case, upper right figure, there is low speed on all sides of the hill, in the non-hydrostatic case, lower right, there is considerable higher speed on the right hand side

Figure 4: Along stream cross-sections through the planes shown in Fig. 3 on the preceding page. The figures show normalized speed and the gray contour line indicate the enforced speed, 0.2 m/s, at the boundaries. The current moves from left to right.

Figure 5: *Vertical profile of normalized speed.*

(looking in the along-stream direction). This indicates that some of the suppressed vertical energy is forcing more of the flow to pass the obstacle along the sides.

5 Results with 1 meter resolution, stratification and grid focusing

The objective for these simulations was to have higher resolution and focus on the obstacle in the center of the domain. During the simulations, which as in the previous were integrated one hour in time, data from a sub-volume, (Fig. 7), has been analyzed.

Along stream cross-sections passing over the highest point on the obstacle is shown in Fig. 8. As in the previous section the contours are normalized speed, and the gray contour-line indicates a normalized speed of unity. In addition streamlines, thin black lines, are added to the figure.

The same features as in Section 4 are present, the increase in speed stretches further in the vertical in the hydrostatic case. Also notice the contraction of streamlines starting on top of the hill that are not present in the non-hydrostatic case. Right in front of the obstacle there is a retardation of the current in both cases. In the hydrostatic case this creates a vertical “channel” of reduced speed. Another difference is the location of maximum speed. In the hydrostatic case there is a speed gain on both sides of the top, in the non-hydrostatic case there is one located right on top of the obstacle.

To see how the flow past the sides of the obstacles behave, horizontal cross-sections at different depths are shown in Fig. 9. Over the top of the hill, the uppermost rows of figures, we see the same features. In the hydrostatic case there is speed gain on both the up-stream and down-stream side of the obstacle, and with a reduction in speed right on top of the hill as the cross-section moves closer. In the non-hydrostatic case the highest gain of speed is right on top of the obstacle and with a reduction of speed on the up-stream side.

As the top of the hill penetrates through the cross-section the flow on the sides becomes quite different. In the hydrostatic case there is a speed reduction all around the obstacle, and with a gain of speed just in front. On the lee side there is a small area with increased speed compared with mean speed. The situation is changed when introducing non-hydrostatic pressure. There is a clear wake behind the top and there is a clear corner effect on the right hand side, looking from upstream.

The reason for this corner effect is; as a water mass approaches a sloping bottom it is forced to move upward. Since the hydrostatic approximation removes a mechanism to transfer some of this

Figure 6: Normalized speed 5 and 10 meters above bottom, and for hydrostatic and non-hydrostatic simulation.

gained vertical velocity to the horizontal the resistance is reduced. On the other hand, when dynamic pressure is present some of this energy is transferred to the horizontal and larger water masses are forced to move past the object on the sides.

Figure 7: The focused grid surrounding the obstacle at which the measuring program was performed.

Figure 8: *Along stream cross-section over the hill in Fig. 7 for hydrostatic and non-hydrostatic simulations. Current moves from left to right.*

6 Discussion and conclusions

The classic gain of energy when a current passes an obstacle has been demonstrated. It has also been shown that the presence of an obstacle may have influence on the current at locations far above the bottom. This is a feature that is not present in today's General Circulation Models hence calls for a proper parameterization of this sub-grid scale effect (Berntsen and Furnes 2002).

App. A gives an overview on the validity of the hydrostatic approximation. In order to identify situations where the approximation is valid a characteristic length scale on the topography is required. This can be obtained by using a method described in Baines (1995) and repeated in App. B. Using this method to obtain μ , A , and B , (Eq. 13 on page 12), gives characteristic obstacle height (2μ), characteristic length (A), and characteristic width (B) of the topography. The topography can be studied by means of repeated characteristic obstacles in stead of the real topography. The exercise gives for the topography used in this report:

$$\begin{aligned}\theta &= -0.55, & \gamma^2 &= 0.7193, \\ 2\mu &= 3.5, & A &= 16, \\ \sigma &= 0.2, & B &= 13.\end{aligned}$$

By using the non-hydrostatic parameter, Eq. 5 on page 11, with $L = O(10)$, (Gill 1982), gives the condition for the validity of the hydrostatic approximation as shown in Fig. 10. It is clear that for the present studies the hydrostatic approximation is not valid. However, since the hydrostatic approximation reduces CPU demands dramatically, whenever justified it should be used.

7 Prospects for future work.

To be able to gain better understanding of the underlying physics, some simulations with simplified topography would be valuable. Apart from looking at simplified Gaussian bumps, simulations on the obstacle in focus of the study in Section 5 and neglecting the rest of the topography should be performed.

A review of the theory behind flow over obstacles should be performed. A good starting point is to review the book by Baines (1995).

Figure 9: Normalized speed in horizontal cross-sections at, from above, 650m, 660m, 664m, and 670 meters depth. Hydrostatic simulation to the left and non-hydrostatic to the right. The current moves from left to right.

Figure 10: The figure shows areas at which the hydrostatic approximation is valid, (lower right area), questionable (gray area), and not valid (upper left) as function of buoyancy frequency and characteristic velocity.

In the present study the stratification has no distinct pycnocline. In the presence of a high vertical density gradient the behavior of internal waves becomes more complex (Baines 1995). Hence further simulations with a distinct pycnocline should be performed, both for a single obstacle and for the full topography. Studies of a time dependent thermocline that flushes over the topography would give even more complex dynamics.

Related to the problems at Ormen Lange; To be able to study as many locations along the pipeline as possible a study that clarifies the influence on the dynamics from the distance to the boundary should be performed. By repeating the present studies with different stretching of the grid, hence different locations of the boundaries, a minimum distance at which the boundary effects are negligible could be identified. Several studies along a pipeline may then be performed at lowest possible CPU cost.

A Hydrostatic vs. non-hydrostatic modeling

General circulation models used on large scales often assumes the hydrostatic approximation. According to Marshall et al. (1997a), this assumption breaks down at a resolution of somewhere between 10 and 1 km as the vertical and horizontal dimensions become comparable. Hence to be able to study the smallest processes in the ocean, a non-hydrostatic solver is necessary.

Considering the equation for the vertical velocity component in the Navier Stokes equations, with the Boussinesq approximation:

$$\frac{Dw}{Dt} + \frac{1}{\rho_0} \frac{\partial \delta p}{\partial z} - b = 0, \quad (1)$$

where δp denotes a deviation from hydrostatically balanced reference state at rest, ρ_0 is a reference density, $b = -g(\partial\rho/\rho_0)$ is the buoyancy, and D/Dt is the total derivative. The hydrostatic approximation is to neglect the Dw/Dt term, hence assuming that $Dw/Dt \ll b$. In the following a flow, with horizontal scale L , vertical scale h , and horizontal velocity scales U is considered. The time scale for a particle to move through the flow will be of the order L/U and by looking at the buoyancy

equation

$$\frac{Db}{Dt_h} + N^2 w = 0, \quad (2)$$

where N^2 is the buoyancy frequency and D/Dt_h is the horizontal component of the total derivative, suggest that a typical vertical velocity will be

$$w \sim \frac{bU}{LN^2}. \quad (3)$$

Hence $Dw/Dt \ll b$ if

$$\frac{U^2}{L^2 N^2} \ll 1. \quad (4)$$

Which is an analog to the conditions for wave motions with U/L replacing ω , see Baines (1995). If the advective timescale is short relative to the buoyancy period the non-hydrostatic effects cannot be neglected. A parameter based on the aspect ratio of the flow ($\gamma = h/L$), and the Richardson number $R_i = N^2 h^2 / U^2$ will be

$$n = \frac{\gamma^2}{R_i}. \quad (5)$$

The motion will be hydrostatic if $n \ll 1$.

The hydrostatic approximation the possibility to prognostically determine the vertical velocity from Eq. (1) is lost. Instead the vertical velocity is diagnostically determined from the continuity equation. In this process an important mechanism for transferring energy between the horizontal and the vertical directions is absent. However, if the current is weak and the stratification is strong the current may still be hydrostatic even if γ is not small.

B Representation of subgrid-scale topography

In all fluid mechanical modeling there are topographic features that are not resolved, so called sub-grid scale (SGS) topography. The usual way to incorporate effects from SGS topography is to include a surface frictional drag with a suitable roughness parameter. Denoting the mean topography over a grid cell by \bar{h} and the true topography by $h(x, y)$, the subgrid orography will be $h_s = h(x, y) - \bar{h}$

For the purpose of proper description of the topography, four other parameters are introduced Baines (1995) . The usual standard variation:

$$\mu = \frac{1}{S} \int \int (h - \bar{h})^2 dS \quad (6)$$

where $\mu[m]$ is the standard deviation and $S[m^2]$ is the area under consideration. As usual 2μ is an approximation to the top of the mountains. And three parameters taken from the *topographic gradient correlation tensor*:

$$H_{ij} = \overline{\frac{\partial h}{\partial x_i} \frac{\partial h}{\partial x_j}} \quad (7)$$

where $x_1 = x$ and $x_2 = y$. The mean is taken over the the whole area of the grid point region. By diagonalizing the tensor we may find principle axes and anisotropy of the sub grid scale topography. By introducing:

$$\mathcal{K} = [(\overline{\frac{\partial h}{\partial x}})^2 + (\overline{\frac{\partial h}{\partial y}})^2]/2, \quad \mathcal{L} = [(\overline{\frac{\partial h}{\partial x}})^2 - (\overline{\frac{\partial h}{\partial y}})^2]/2, \quad \mathcal{M} = \overline{\frac{\partial h}{\partial x} \frac{\partial h}{\partial y}} \quad (8)$$

the principal axis of H_{ij} is oriented at an angle

$$\theta = \frac{1}{2} \arctan\left(\frac{\mathcal{M}}{\mathcal{L}}\right) \quad (9)$$

to the x-axis. Topographic variations are largest along the principal direction, and the direction of minimum variation is perpendicular. By a co-ordinate transformation orienting the axis to these two direction:

$$x' = x \cos \theta + y \sin \theta, \quad y' = y \cos \theta - x \sin \theta \quad (10)$$

the new values in (8)

$$\mathcal{K}' = \mathcal{K}, \quad \mathcal{L}' = (\mathcal{L}^2 + \mathcal{M}^2)^{\frac{1}{2}}, \quad \mathcal{M}' = 0 \quad (11)$$

The anisotropy of the orography is given by the aspect ratio

$$\gamma^2 = \frac{(\overline{\frac{\partial h}{\partial y'}})^2}{(\overline{\frac{\partial h}{\partial x'}})^2} = \frac{\mathcal{K}' - \mathcal{L}'}{\mathcal{K}' + \mathcal{L}'} \leq 1. \quad (12)$$

from these we may define mean square slope σ^2 along the principle axis and associated length scales A and B by

$$\sigma^2 = \left(\overline{\frac{\partial h}{\partial x'}}\right)^2, \quad \left(\frac{A}{2}\right)^2 = \frac{\mu^2}{\sigma^2}, \quad B^2 = \gamma^2 A^2 \quad (13)$$

The quantities \bar{h} , μ , σ , γ and θ describe the topography. As an example, consider a periodic h

$$h(x', y') = h_0(1 + \cos kx' \cos my') \quad k \geq m,$$

then

$$\bar{h} = h_0, \quad \mu = h_0/2, \quad \sigma = kh_0/2, \quad \gamma = m/k, \quad (14)$$

and $A = \pi/k$, $B = \pi/m$.

The subgrid scale topography is statistically uniform if the statistical quantities are equal for any sufficiently large subregions of the SGS topography. For statistically uniform topography; From μ , σ , γ and θ we may identify a representative obstacle with height 2μ and known shape and orientation that characterize the topography. *The problem of specifying the effect from the complex terrain is thus replaced by finding effects of a single repetitional obstacle.*

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